

Nuclear science education and training in Ethiopia: Status and prospects

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Abstract

This study examines the current status, challenges, and future prospects of nuclear science education and training (E&T) in Ethiopia. Nuclear education began in the 1960s with basic theoretical concepts, and the first structured academic efforts emerged in the 1990s through MSc program at Addis Ababa University. However, there are still no dedicated undergraduate degrees or specialized training programs in nuclear science. To identify a path forward, the study compares Ethiopia's progress with selected developed countries that have successfully leveraged nuclear technology, emphasizing the importance of collaboration and shared experience. The study focuses on four essential pillars: human resource development, knowledge management, knowledge networks, and long-term sustainability. It aims to serve as a communication tool for both national policymakers and institutions to support the growth of nuclear E&T in alignment with Ethiopia's development goals. Major challenges include inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, lack of qualified personnel, and insufficient laboratory facilities. If Ethiopia's present nuclear energy ambitions are to succeed, the government will require competent human resources to develop nuclear facilities, assure safe and secure operations, and conduct nuclear E&T and research. To address these needs, the study recommends developing internationally aligned curricula, investing in skilled faculty and technicians, expanding research infrastructure, and building public trust through awareness and education. The paper concludes by highlighting the critical role of international and national collaboration in strengthening nuclear education in Ethiopia and presents practical recommendations to guide future development in areas such as energy, health, agriculture, industry, and other disciplines.

Keywords

Ethiopia, higher education, nuclear education, training, human resources development, collaboration

Introduction

Ethiopian nuclear science education began with physics and chemistry classes in high school, which covered theoretical nuclear science topics. In the late 1960s, Emperor Haile Selassie Hospital used radiation technology for medical facilities (IAEA 1969). A cross-cutting issue that is vital to the nuclear industry is nuclear education. Researchers in both academic and industrial settings have paid close attention to the interaction be-

tween industry and academics in the creation and application of new information (Cizelj et al. 2023). There is a turning moment in Ethiopian nuclear science education and training, although it is not yet at a crisis point or under stress. At the same time, the industry's needs have decreased in terms of research and recruitment. Although Ethiopia has no nuclear engineering education and the nuclear physics for postgraduate study, which is insufficient to provide in-depth insights due to the curriculum and infrastructure.

The present study seeks to underline the significance of nuclear E&T at the bachelor's and higher education levels in Ethiopia. The purpose is to explore the vital role that nuclear education, training, and research can play in strengthening Ethiopia's capacity to adopt and safely utilize nuclear technologies. Ethiopia is one of the African nations with an active nuclear program that does not currently have a nuclear power reactor in operation. Research reactors are the most important experimental facilities for accomplishing the goal of nuclear education (Radulović et al. 2021). This suggests that there is little to no foundation for nuclear science and technology (NS&T) in Ethiopia's research activities and educational and training system. The sustainable development of nuclear energy, healthcare, and agricultural productivity are all significantly aided by human resources. Nuclear science and technology play a critical role in addressing some of the most pressing challenges of our time. Initiatives on this fields are aimed at students and recent graduates, young professionals, national officers, and nuclear specialists and technicians from diverse communities (Michailidou et al. 2024). However, one of the issues preventing nuclear energy from developing further worldwide is a shortage of human resources (Guo and Lamb 2010). One of the main drivers of human progress in the past century, nuclear research makes a substantial contribution to clean energy and cutting-edge healthcare globally (Dieguez Porras et al. 2024). Nuclear E&T is essential for Ethiopia and the rest of the globe in order to educate and train individuals to fulfill the expected demands for recruits in the nuclear industry (Čerba et al. 2024). For power, food safety, agriculture, space exploration, isotope manufacturing for cancer therapy or medical diagnostics, and many more exciting non-power nuclear applications (Hartini et al. 2023; Plan and April 2002; Sisay Mekonen 2023), a skilled, trained workforce must be preserved and expanded (Seibert et al. 2024). Globally, NS&T has been contributing tremendously toward the advancement of science, technology, and the socioeconomic sector and has the capacity to save lives (Energy et al. 1995) and truly serve humanity (Holcomb 1999).

The safe functioning of present nuclear facilities and the application of current knowledge to the creation of novel strategies for the nuclear sector depend heavily on nuclear knowledge management (Sheet 2023). One of the most crucial resources for nuclear technology, which encompasses numerous scientific and engineering fields, is knowledge, which must be carefully controlled (Janssens-maenhout and Daures 2009). Nuclear science and engineering programs at universities are essential to increasing the value of nuclear technology globally. In addition, Ethiopia should expand nuclear E&T at the high school, college, and graduate levels in order to carefully concentrate on nuclear knowledge management. In developed countries, nuclear engineering at the undergraduate and graduate levels is one of the most crucial aspects of nuclear education. A viable and well-defined topic of study, nuclear engineering offers specially qual-

ified engineers to work in engineering and scientific domains pertaining to the utilization of nuclear energy and nuclear radiation for industrial and scientific purposes, as well as other disciplines (Martin 1993). In addition to working to establish and advance nuclear technology, the nuclear engineering department seeks to prepare students to become nuclear engineers who can contribute scientifically to the peaceful applications of nuclear energy (Oner 2008).

In affluent nations today, nuclear research is far more advanced than this, yet not in Ethiopia. In order to create wealth, improve people's quality of life, and achieve true economic progress and change in any community, technology becomes vital (Anaeto et al. 2016). Based on these, Ethiopia concentrated on creating a program in nuclear science and technology to enhance living standards and boost economic growth for the following generation. The capacity of local educational institutions to produce scientists, engineers, and technicians is a major factor in the success of a nuclear program in a developing nation (Document et al. 1981). Ethiopia should establish a strong connection between nuclear science education and training at universities and the construction of nuclear power plants that will supply electricity in the future. Ethiopian Nuclear Science Society (ENSS), Ethiopian Technology Authority (ETA), Ethiopian Nuclear Science Education Technology (Eth-NEST), and other established and continuing organizations that seek to enhance nuclear E&T. In order to build NS&T for various applications, it is necessary to reformulate the old teaching programs into the new one to be able to transfer a similar quantity of information and abilities as included in the previous programs through various means and to obtain trained labor (Ambrosini and Cirillo 2024).

The study is limited to nuclear E&T because education and integrated training are vital information providers, character molders, knowledge networks, continuous learning, and human resources development, which have always been the footing of individual and institutional development of nuclear programs in Ethiopia. Comparisons between Ethiopian nuclear education and a few chosen developed nations were made. These comparisons serve as a foundation for developing nations to begin and progress nuclear education for human capacity building and for peaceful use in several aspects, as described below. They also demonstrate how countries began and progressed nuclear education and training.

Review of nuclear education for selected country

Several countries have developed nuclear knowledge recently and have been enjoying using the benefits of nuclear technology in various contexts. The following nations were chosen by the researcher in order to show their success in the field due to their advanced nuclear

E&T research programs. This data has been documented and is available via the internet. The researcher has collected these data and compared them with Ethiopia to emphasize how to use the nuclear facility peacefully for the sharing of experience and resources and to follow their lead through collaborations to advance nuclear E&T in Ethiopia.

Russia

The Moscow Engineering Physics Institute (MEPHI) has a 60-year history of being a unique system of nuclear engineering professionals' training (Kryuchkov 2008). MEPHI will serve as the leader of the National Nuclear Research University (Duncan et al. 2012). Free nuclear education is offered in Russia, along with BSc, MSc, and PhD programs at universities that export nuclear education (Guide 2024). Like all other knowledge domains, nuclear engineering education in Russia consists of training activities that are only restricted by Russian law. All of these colleges offer nuclear engineering specialist training in complete compliance with common educational curricula and standards that outline some of the specifics of this type of instruction (Kryuchkov 2008), and nuclear technologies also form the foundation for economic, energy and political security (Murogov et al. 2009). Russia views nuclear technologies as a potent tool for creating a high-tech economy and reducing reliance on raw material exports through the growth of high-tech businesses, with education playing a crucial role in this process (Viktor Murogov et al. 2013). Russia's nuclear weapons program directly led to the development of its nuclear energy sector more than 50 years ago (Davis 2009). 58 of the 245 nuclear research reactors in operation worldwide are located in Russia. Russia's nuclear-security systems are currently quite effective, according to the Russian government's repeated claims (Bunn and Kovchegin 2017).

United States of America (USA)

The United States' nuclear education history began in the 1960s and continued until the 1980s, when there were about 64 university research reactors, 50 nuclear engineering programs, a large number of students, and the ordering and construction of plants (Kent Hamlin, Experience 2009). Since there was little need for engineers with a bachelor's degree at the time, many nuclear engineering programs started in the early to late 1950s and initially concentrated on graduate education (Martin 1993). For nuclear technology to contribute to US's energy supply, ecology, health care, and national security, human resources are crucial (Statement 2022). The American Nuclear Society (ANS) is in favor of long-term, comprehensive stewardship of nuclear education and training initiatives because of this. A Nuclear Science & Engineering Education Sourcebook has been released by the Office of Nuclear Energy and the Ameri-

can Nuclear Society (ANS) for education, training, and workforce division. These reference materials are meant to help academics, students, businesses, and government organizations collaborate on nuclear research, education, and service projects. Since 1986, US researchers have been collecting crucial information on nuclear engineering faculty enrollment, degrees, and competency in print and electronic media (American Nuclear Society 1976). The collected data from 23 Ph.D.-granting physics departments, averaging 20 or more physics majors annually for the most recent accessible years (1999–2001), to measure exposure to nuclear science throughout the undergraduate years (Report 2004).

United Kingdom, UK

Beginning with the initial stage of nuclear construction in the early 1950s, the University of Birmingham in the United Kingdom has a long and distinguished history of working in the fields of applied and fundamental nuclear science, nuclear data, decommissioning, health monitoring, and residual life prediction of existing nuclear power stations. The needs of the nuclear industry both now and in the future, as well as how social and economic policies are influencing the environment, are the main emphasis of the University of Birmingham (Birmingham and Uk 2013). Because nuclear energy is safe, dependable, and clean, the UK government is clear about how vital it is to the energy mix and is working to make sure that the market can and will support the development of new nuclear power (HM Government 2013). By the late 2020s, all but one of the 16 nuclear reactors that currently provide 20% of the UK's total electricity will be retired. About 11% of the electricity produced worldwide comes from nuclear power, with the UK consuming 20% on average (NI 2013). To provide a long-term structure for delivering the national policy in nuclear energy and monitoring progress along a predetermined roadmap, the government should establish a statutory nuclear policy council, or something akin to the committee on climate change (Gudkova 2017).

South Korea

The late 1950s saw the start of interest in nuclear energy. One of the founding nations of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in 1957 was South Korea. In 1959, the Korean atomic energy research institute and an atomic energy commission were founded by the government (Yang and Yi-chong 2011). There are five stages to the Korean nuclear energy development program, which began in the 1960s (Min et al. 2004). There are six universities that provide BSc, MSc, and Ph.D. programs in nuclear engineering. The government is in charge of nuclear power planning, regulation, control, and policy and promotion. Over the past ten years, Korea has seen an increase in radiation and its numerous industrial uses of about 10 percent annually (Son et al. 2012). It is cru-

cial for South Korea to increase nuclear power and use radiation as a source of energy in compliance with the climate change convention, energy security concerns, and general national welfare (Choi et al. 2020). Over the past few decades, South Korea's civil nuclear energy program has grown significantly, reached a high degree of self-sufficiency, established a strong and diverse nuclear research and development program, and started participating in international nuclear cooperation. One of the world's leading nuclear power initiatives is now nuclear energy (Mcgoldrick 2015).

China

China has developed its nuclear technology over the course of more than 50 years. As soon as it made the decision to build nuclear power, in the early 1980s, China planned to close its nuclear fuel cycle (Chen et al. 2018). The National Nuclear Safety Administration (NNSA) was established by the State Council in 1984 and given the responsibility of overseeing the security of China's civil nuclear plants (Abou-Donia 2015). The largest platform in the world for the use of nuclear technology to produce electricity is currently the People's Republic of China (Hibbs 2018). Hundreds of graduates are dispatched annually to nuclear energy research and development organizations and businesses by China's more than a dozen colleges with nuclear-related specialists. In China, nuclear activities are carried out by the following entities: government agencies, regulatory bodies, business owners, universities, institutes, and operators (Guo and Lamb 2010). Additionally, universities and other institutions have almost 20 research reactors and other nuclear installations. China has the most aggressive nuclear plant plans in the world, yet no country has as many planned nuclear reactors specifically specified. All nuclear projects must be approved by the state development and planning commission, which suggests the significance of using nuclear technology and nuclear research in a peaceful manner (Kadak 2005).

Japan

The major course on the history of nuclear engineering in Japan began in 1957 (N Masayoshi Uno Engineering 2023). In Japan, industry, hospitals, research institutes, and educational institutions all make extensive use of nuclear and high energy radiation as well as different radioisotopes (Takashima 1993). A countrywide university is essential for research and education on the use of nuclear fuel materials that require facilities, as nuclear education in Japan can no longer be fulfilled by a single institution. Nuclear engineering education was completely established in 2004 with the start of the nuclear power & energy safety program in the university of Fukui's graduate school of engineering. The research institute of nuclear engineering opened its doors in 2009, and in 2016, school of engineering offered undergraduate nuclear education (Power 2015). Furthermore, one of Japan's most significant energy sources nowadays is nuclear power.

Romania

The history of Romania's nuclear power program begins in the 1960s, when the country first contacted suppliers (Dragusin and Burghilea, n.d.). The first academic course on nuclear power plants was created in 1967, and the first postgraduate program was implemented the following year. The department of nuclear power plants became a member of the faculty of electrical engineering in 1970. The name was changed to the department of nuclear engineering in 2001 in accordance with new national university standards. Since its inception, 920 students have graduated with a five-year nuclear engineering specialization, and since 1998, 58 master's students have graduated (Ghitescu et al. 2005). In order to meet the needs of the nuclear industry (nuclear power plants, regulatory bodies, subcontractors, dismantling, radioprotection, waste management), as well as the viewpoints of the European Union and regional research initiatives, the Romanian Network of Excellence in Nuclear Physics and Engineering (REFIN) aims to develop a modern nuclear education training system (Ghitescu 2009).

History of nuclear science education in Ethiopia

Early in the late 1960s, Ethiopia began nuclear education and training. Some basic theoretical ideas of nuclear science are taught in high school, mostly in physics and chemistry classes (IAEA 1969). Using a little isotope, the country's pathobiology institute attempted to develop nuclear applications. The Institute of Pathobiology was founded at the Haile Selassie I university of science in 1967–69. According to the report, since 1967, when it was first started, the course of "nuclear science techniques" has gained momentum and student enrollment is rising. Freshmen are once again introduced to nuclear science aspects in physics, chemistry, and biology courses without any accompanying laboratory work or demonstrations. The utilization of radioisotopes for teaching and research purposes is greatly aided by the biology department. In 1972, the course was greatly broadened to cover not only simply physical issues but also biological, industrial, and medicinal applications of radioisotopes. For the advantage of the workforce, a more specialized and intense nuclear technique training was planned and conducted this year. The IAEA technical assistance program provided the equipment items for the newly founded institute, which were mainly employed for research purposes employing alpha and gamma counters and a 2500 curie cobalt-60 irradiation source. An agreement for the application of nuclear safeguards in accordance with the non-proliferation treaty was signed by Ethiopia and the IAEA in 1977. Early in the late 1990s, the National Radiation Protection Authority (NRPA) was founded next to a pathobiology institute. These NRPA

have a unique organizational design (Mastauskas 1999), legislative framework and seeks to support and stimulate radiation protection research and development. Nuclear facilities organized and equipped NRPA at the turn of the century. These facilities include a computerized Solar TLD reader for personal monitoring of radiation workers nationwide, a Hyper Purity Germanium (HPGe) and a low-resolution sodium iodide (NaI) gamma ray spectroscopy system with all the electronics and software needed, an alpha spectrometry system with a silicon (Si) surface barrier detector, quality assurance test kits, and various dose measuring devices. In the secondary standard calibration bunker, a 20 curie (Ci) Cesium source, a small instrumentation and maintenance unit, and an X-ray machine with the accessories are installed for the purpose of calibrating a radiation dosimetry instrument. Now known as the Ethiopian Technology Authority (ETA), NRPA focuses on nuclear method application research and training across various fields.

The idea of nuclear medicine was first introduced in the internal medicine department of AAU in 1984 in collaboration with the Ministry of Health and the IAEA. AAU Black Lion Specialized Hospital launched the curriculum-developed nuclear medicine specialization in 2018 with a small number of nuclear medicine specialists. The first PhD program in nuclear physics was initiated in 2006 at the Addis Ababa University Department of Physics by both local and foreign nuclear experts, while the master's program began in the early 1990s. Organizations such as ETA and AAU, a university that produces the majority of Ethiopia's master's and doctoral degrees in nuclear physics, are essential to the development of qualified professionals and nuclear science research. There are also no nuclear research institutions, and starting in 2015, the IAEA-donated facility was unable to resupply the experimental activities, which gradually moved to computer models. The first national centralized radioactive waste processing and storage facility was established in Addis Ababa in 2014, and new industrial irradiator equipment was installed at the Kality Tsetse fly mass-rearing facility to sterilize disease-carrying pests.

About ten universities currently offer MSc programs and only the AAU PhD program in nuclear and radiation physics, out of more than 45 public and private universities and no specific nuclear engineering education or but no full nuclear-focused degree programs are widely available yet in any Ethiopian higher education systems. This is insufficient to produce skilled individuals in nuclear science and technology due to the curriculum and lack of enthusiasm in the field. Established in August 2021 in accordance with the proclamations of Ethiopian civil society organizations, the Ethiopian Nuclear Science Society (ENSS) is the nation's first professional society in the field of nuclear science. Its mission is to raise public awareness and understanding of NST, advocate for the safe and responsible use of nuclear energy for power generation, medical purposes, and other applications, support research and development in NS&T and offer education

and training opportunities for professionals and students pursuing careers in nuclear science. Established in December 2023 and formally inaugurated on February 2, 2024, the Ethiopian Network for Nuclear Education and Technology (Eth-NEST) aims to become Africa's premier network for the advancement of nuclear education and technology (Tesfaye 2024). Eth-NEST seeks to enhance capacity, encourage research collaborations, advance information exchange, and expand nuclear programs.

Ethiopia's Ministry of Innovation and Technology (MinT) has conducted studies and feasibility analyses of potential nuclear power facilities and established a national nuclear task force in 2021. In response to the need assessment and lack of human resources in the field of nuclear science and technology, the Ethiopian government has recognized the need to explore nuclear power and other alternative energy sources and NS&T as one of the key development tools, as evidenced by the plan to establish Excellence centers. Bahir Dar University (BDU), Addis Ababa Science and Technology University (AASTU) recently launched an MSc program in Nuclear Science and Engineering, a center for Nuclear Reactor Technology, and plans to increase its capabilities in this area. Although there have been some recent advancements in the nation's nuclear science and technology education base and national education system, there are currently no explicit policies or regulations pertaining to standardization and modularization (IAEA 2011). Besides, the nation lacks conventional universities offering programs in nuclear and radiological sciences, nuclear engineering or technology, and radiopharmaceuticals.

The mission of the energy department and nuclear scientific foundation to promote the general welfare of society and to help maintain Ethiopia's competitiveness in the field of nuclear sciences and technology is mostly supported by education and outreach. Since Ethiopia is experiencing a potentially severe shortage of skilled workers in pure and applied nuclear science research, nuclear medicine, nuclear energy, nuclear engineering, nuclear security & safeguards, and related fields, it is imperative that the next generation of workers be educated in nuclear science. The benefits of nuclear science are frequently not well understood by the public or even by scientists in other fields (Tribble 2008). The standard university physics courses teach the fundamentals of nuclear science. As more colleges were prepared to offer these kinds of courses and more in-depth expertise in nuclear science and technology, the quantity and caliber of instruction increased over time (Nations and Council 1995).

Main challenges for Ethiopian nuclear program

Ethiopia faces significant regulatory and funding challenges that hinder the development of its nuclear education and training system. Some of the main difficulties are:

- **Lack of local nuclear technology expertise:** There are few professionals with nuclear-related credentials, there is a high turnover rate of skilled workers, foreign experts are relied upon for the initial stages, extensive training programs are required to develop local expertise, there are no specialized nuclear engineering programs, and expatriates and foreign experts are used.
- **Lack of existing nuclear infrastructure:** Universities and research centers often lack the physical and technical infrastructure required for practical training and experimentation. No nuclear facilities or reactors are in operation, there are no nuclear research institutes.
- **Regulatory & funding gaps:** On the regulatory side, there is a lack of clear, updated national policies and legal frameworks specifically tailored to support nuclear science education, research, and peaceful applications of nuclear technology.
In terms of funding, there is insufficient and inconsistent government financial support for nuclear-related programs, infrastructure, and research. Universities and research institutions often lack the necessary resources to develop modern curricula, purchase laboratory equipment, offer scholarships, or train and retain qualified faculty in nuclear fields.
- **Inadequate nuclear engineering education programs:** There aren't many programs specifically focused on nuclear engineering, and the courses that are offered mostly cover nuclear physics. Curriculum development and staff training are also needed. It has not yet been possible to achieve unified coordination and collaboration that maximizes resources at the local level.
- **Limited international collaboration:** Insufficient engagement with global nuclear institutions reduces access to training opportunities, technology transfer, and resource sharing.

Role of international cooperation in development of nuclear education and training

Within the past few years, the importance of international cooperation in the advancement of education has grown enormously (Kryuchkov 2008). According to the scholar, "Science knows no borders." Indeed, scientists frequently relocate and work together across borders, giving them access to "multiple learning environments," typically resulting in more impactful research, and elevating their stature (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al. 2017). The innovation process can benefit greatly from cooperation with international partners since it enables businesses to share risks and obtain access to a larger pool of resources and expertise at a reduced cost (Science 2011). Collaboration at the regional, national, and

international levels is a driving force behind changes in training and education (Ai-Youbi et al. 2019) and it is more appealing to policymakers and scientists alike (U.S. Congress 1995). The idea of worldwide cooperation in the realm of education is supported by the concept of collaborative learning (Espino 2018). Reasons for partnership (Wagner et al. 2001) encompass joint research and technology development, support for the organization of technological demonstrations, and the fact that different countries have distinct capacities for implementing scientific research and technological development (Bouchard 2005). Universities, research centers, and industry must collaborate to better coordinate their efforts in order to inspire the next generation. It is crucial to create and advance a program of cooperation in nuclear education and training and to offer a way for Member nations to exchange best practices in promoting nuclear courses (NEA 2000). Educational networks, which facilitate the exchange of information, experiences, and best practices, have a substantial positive impact on education (Introduction. A 2002). Ethiopia should also increase its cooperation with developed nations in order to address public concerns and regulate and manage nuclear energy (Yang et al. 2016). The need to address some common educational issues, such as those pertaining to nuclear engineering education, and global tendencies toward integration are the main causes of this expansion (Kryuchkov 2008).

Ethiopia has signed educational and technical agreements with countries like Russia, China, and South Korea, which include scholarships, fellowships, faculty training, and to support the growth of its nuclear industry, based on the value of cooperation. A Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on cooperation in the peaceful use of nuclear energy was signed by Russia and Ethiopia in 2019. Russia has promised to assist Ethiopia in a number of areas under this agreement, such as scientific investigation, workforce training, nuclear infrastructure development, and feasibility studies. A research reactor, a multifunctional radiation center, a nuclear medicine center, and labs for producing radioisotopes for use in industry, agriculture, and health-care might all be part of the Centre for Nuclear Science and Technology (CNST). Thus, we can see that the CNST has great potential and its construction in Ethiopia is very relevant to become a platform for training highly qualified personnel for the nuclear industry and contribute to research in digital technology as well. Ethiopia needs more collaborations with other developed nations in the field of nuclear science for technical assistance and training programs, access to international research and development, and the most important development of nuclear education should be presented in the integration of universities into international networks.

Ethiopia should work with well-run organizations and network as a state member of the African Network for Education in Nuclear Science and Technology (AFRA-NEST) to enhance nuclear science education and human resource development. AFRA-NEST's primary goal is to

support networking and operations in NS&T higher education, training, and related research in the African region by exchanging resources, encouraging efficient collaboration, facilitating student, teacher, and researcher exchanges, etc., (Hashim 2017). For the purpose of advancing the national nuclear program in the future, the AFRA NEST member state developed its nuclear scientific education and human resource development. To guarantee a skilled and trained labor in the operational organizations, supply chain, and industrial, agricultural, and medical sectors, nuclear education networks must implement focused and efficient educational programs in their member states.

Future prospects of nuclear E&T

Successful workforce development through a long-term nuclear education and training program backed by the government and industry is essential to the growth of any national nuclear energy program (IAEA 2014). For the next generation and to draw future prospects to nuclear-related occupations, it is crucial to concentrate on nuclear education, research, and training. Students who receive instruction in nuclear engineering gain a thorough understanding of nuclear physics, reactor design, radiation protection, and related topics.

To meet future energy demands and ensure safe and secure operations, nuclear engineering education is critical. Therefore, the following should be the necessity of acting and the Ethiopian government's principal objectives:

- Examine how experiential learning can aid students in developing a deeper understanding of nuclear concepts and consider how specialized nuclear labs provide interdisciplinary applications that link fields such as environmental research, healthcare, and agriculture.
- The government should create a statutory Nuclear Policy Council to boost the nuclear education and training and should be responsible for the policy and promotion, planning of nuclear power, and regulatory and control system.
- In the future of nuclear power plant which satisfies the electricity needs Ethiopia should closely link and promote nuclear education and training program at universities, keeping a qualified nuclear professional in industries and fostering global combativeness of nuclear manpower.
- The introduction and implementation of guided tours around nuclear power plants could also be one of the future initiatives to raise awareness of nuclear power.
- Governments should support extensive, well-known, international research and development programs that draw students and young professionals to become the nuclear experts needed in the future, regardless of whether they decide to use nuclear power. Second, the entire spectrum of practice-oriented information and skills required for professional activities cannot be taught in nuclear university

programs. This includes providing financial support to universities and student scholarships.

Additionally, a component of the nuclear education and training plan should be approved by legislation and should establish an organization similar to the Ethiopian National Strategy for Nuclear Energy Development (ENNS). The Annual Nuclear Plan (ANP) and the National Nuclear Program (NNP) are the instruments used to carry out ENNS. Both plans include general guidelines for the advancement of nuclear training and education in the future that align with the objectives of the network.

The country has created relationships with numerous foreign organizations and colleges to enhance the educational infrastructure and stimulate information exchange. To maintain the Ethiopian competitiveness, it is essential that federal and state governments, industry, foundations, educational institutions, and other stakeholders support education in the fundamentals of nuclear technology, university nuclear engineering programs and technical E&T for nuclear science and skilled manpower. In situations where required actions would not be taken without government, governments are accountable for taking steps that are obviously in the long-term national interest of their countries [N Masayoshi Uno 2023]. Ethiopia should prioritize nuclear education at the high school, bachelor's, master's, and doctoral levels in accordance with the scope of nuclear engineering programs. Building a nuclear research institution should be Ethiopia's top priority in order to enhance the nation's socioeconomic standing through applications in industry, agriculture, medicine, and the environment, to enhance nuclear education and programs and meet the needs of corporate communities and stakeholders.

How a nuclear education and training can be established?

The researcher suggests a structured four-stage approach to establish a national nuclear program. This framework includes awareness, coordination, nuclear society, and development as key pillars for sustainable progress.

Proposed solution for advancing NE&T in Ethiopia

Addressing the gaps is essential for building a robust nuclear science and technology sector in Ethiopia. It requires coordinated efforts to establish a strong regulatory framework and increase investment from both public and private sources. The researcher put forward the proposed solution for ensuring nuclear education and training in Ethiopia, the goal being to reestablish nuclear science by setting up the learning system, training syllabus and research in different topics. Specifically:

Figure 1. Scope of nuclear engineering academic programmes (IAEA 2014). The figure presents a comprehensive overview of the core and supporting components of a nuclear engineering academic program at the bachelor's and master's levels, including technical fields. It also emphasizes critical support areas like radiation protection, safety and security, and safeguards. This structured and integrated approach can guide the development of Ethiopia's nuclear E&T program by ensuring that future graduates are equipped with both the technical expertise and leadership capabilities needed to support the country's peaceful nuclear ambitions across sectors like energy, health, agriculture, and industry and drive innovations.

Figure 2. Four-stage suggested approach to develop nuclear program.

Figure 3. Future Nuclear Program in Ethiopia.

- **Strengthen nuclear education programs**
 - Integrate nuclear science and technology into undergraduate and postgraduate programs in Ethiopian universities.
 - Develop specialized tracks in medical physics, radiochemistry, nuclear engineering, and radiation safety.
 - Partner with the IAEA and international universities for curriculum development and academic exchanges.
- **Expand technical and vocational training**
 - Establish national training centers focused on hands-on nuclear techniques (e.g., radiological labs, isotope production, Non-Distractive Testing).
 - Implement certificate and diploma programs in partnership with technical colleges and international agencies.
 - Promote internships and apprenticeships in hospitals, research centers, and industry facilities.
- **Promote nuclear research and innovation**
 - Create dedicated research labs for applied nuclear research in health, agriculture, and environmental monitoring.
 - Fund priority research projects aligned with national development goals.

Figure 4. How can fundamental research in nuclear science contribute to long term development?

- Encourage collaborative research with regional centers of excellence and international institutions.
- **Build institutional capacity and governance**
 - Develop a national strategy and policy framework for nuclear education, research, and capacity building.
 - Strengthen the Ethiopian Technology Authority (ETA), Ministry of Innovation and technology (MinT) and its collaboration with ministries of education, health, and agriculture.
 - Establish a central coordinating body for nuclear science capacity building.
- **Increase public awareness and stakeholder engagement**
 - Conduct nationwide awareness campaigns on the benefits and safety of nuclear applications.
 - Involve media, civil society, and educational institutions in public education.
 - Engage policy-makers, educators, and industry leaders through forums and dialogues.

Conclusion

This paper explores the current state of nuclear education and training (E&T) in Ethiopia and proposes forward-looking initiatives to strengthen sustainability and advance nuclear science and technology (NS&T). By comparing Ethiopia's progress with that of selected developed nations, the study highlights opportunities for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and shared resource development to support national capacity building. The focus on nuclear E&T stems from its essential role in shaping skilled professionals, fostering knowledge networks, and supporting human resource development key drivers of both institutional and national progress. Establishing structured degree programs at the undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral levels in nuclear engineering and related fields should be prioritized to increase the number of qualified experts across academia, industry, and public institutions.

Universities must play a central role in producing the next generation of nuclear professionals. To ensure long-

term impact, Ethiopia should actively engage with regional, national, and international partners to improve the quality of education, promote technology transfer, and encourage participation in global forums, training programs, and research initiatives. Ultimately, education, training, and research are the pillars of national development in NS&T. A coordinated effort involving government, academic institutions, industry, and civil society is vital to expanding infrastructure, building public trust, and aligning policy support. With clear direction and sustained commitment, Ethiopia can harness nuclear technology to advance healthcare, agriculture, energy, and industrial development, laying the foundation for a more innovative and sustainable future.

Recommendations

The following key recommendations are proposed to promote the growth of nuclear science and technology in Ethiopia by building capacity, strengthening institutions, and fostering national and international collaboration.

- **Integrate nuclear education:** The Ministry of Education should revise curricula to include nuclear science basics in lower grades and expand undergraduate and postgraduate nuclear engineering programs.
- **Support key institutions:** Provide financial and technical support to organizations like ETA, ENSS, Eth-NEST, and universities to build skilled professionals and promote a strong radiation safety culture.
- **Promote research:** The government and relevant institutions should lead and fund nuclear research, supporting a national task force to develop authoritative references on Ethiopian nuclear science.
- **Seek international support:** Collaborate with the global nuclear community for technical, financial, and training assistance.
- **Adopt Public-Private Partnerships (PPP):** Encourage PPPs to share the cost and responsibility of developing nuclear infrastructure.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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